

Facing the Limits: Designing Data Physicalizations to Reduce Water Consumption in Mountain Huts

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ABSTRACT

Mountain huts are buildings in remote mountain areas that depend on local water sources, such as snow, rain, and springs, as they are not connected to centralized water systems. In this pictorial, we report the design process undertaken to explore how data physicalization can communicate the problem of water scarcity in mountain huts with the ultimate goal of encouraging visitors to reduce water usage. The process led to two concepts: one that materializes the impact of each visitor on the water reserve of the hut through a participatory installation, and the other that invites visitors to explore the concept of limit, encouraging reflection on what they are willing to renounce and helping them to make informed choices within tight water constraints. With our work, we aim to contribute to the ongoing efforts in Sustainable HCI to shift the purpose of behavior change from personal gain to the common good.

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Data physicalization; water; mountain huts; climate change.

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- Human-centered computing~Visualization systems and tools

INTRODUCTION

Water scarcity is a global issue: “roughly half of the world’s population currently experiences severe water scarcity for at least part of the year” [10]. Mountains are already facing the effects of the water crisis, acting as a crucial early warning system for global issues related to climate change [6]. Mountain huts are buildings in mountainous or remote areas that offer visitors meals and overnight stays in dormitories.

Their primary role is to ensure essential safety for hikers, climbers, and backcountry skiers (in fact, they are also known as ‘shelters’). They use water for cooking and dishwashing, cleaning, personal hygiene, and, in some cases, also for energy production through small hydropower stations. As for drinking water, it is usually bottled and supplied as all the other food for sanitation reasons. Since mountain huts are not connected to urban water systems, their survival depends on the efficient management of their limited water resources. But, as glaciers and snowfields shrink and precipitation becomes less predictable and constant due to global warming, huts face severe challenges securing water through traditional methods like snowfield piping or rainwater collection.

Through semi-structured interviews, we explored the challenges 12 Trentino mountain hut managers face regarding water management. The managers were selected because they had experienced water scarcity or installed interesting solutions to limit water consumption. Each interview explored various topics, including i) types of water supply for the hut (e.g., spring, snowmelt) and storage capacity; ii) perception of the water scarcity problem and strategies adopted to tackle emergencies; iii) practices to raise awareness of water scarcity in guests. The interviews lasted 90 minutes on average. The audio was recorded and then transcribed. For the analysis, we followed a Reflexive Thematic Analysis approach [3].

The main issue emerging from interviews is that visitors’ water consumption significantly impacts the huts’ water resources. At the same time, visitors have a limited understanding of how huts operate regarding water provision and use, and do not fully understand the limitations and the specific needs of these structures, thus increasing pressure on an already scarce resource. A central topic that emerged is the necessity to enhance reflection on the limits of natural resources. These issues align with concerns raised in the HCI community that is discussing how interactive systems might support drought crises [15] and, more broadly, a post-growth society where consumption is

framed as a trade-off between human well-being and planetary limits [21] (cf. the LIMITS workshop series <https://computingwithinlimits.org/>).

In this work, we explore how data physicalization, i.e., “artifacts whose geometrical shape or material properties encode data” [1, 9], can be used to turn data on water scarcity and individual water consumption into physical, tangible shapes that enable a deeper understanding of the impact each visitor entails on the collective life of a mountain hut. The choice of making data tangible by embedding it into physical artifacts is due to the peculiar context in which mountain huts are located. In the mountains, electricity provision might be intermittent, and internet connectivity is not guaranteed, so we preferred not to rely on screen-based interfaces such as videogames or websites. Furthermore, we aimed to leverage the capacity of data physicalization to enhance users’ understanding and retention of information and to broaden participation by allowing them to interact with data physically. The tactile experience offered by physicalizations is expected to improve the interaction and engagement with data, making data more accessible and, thus, promoting data literacy and enabling non-experts to engage with complex datasets [9].

Being situated in fragile and resource-scarce environments, mountain huts provide a distinctive perspective for examining the developing patterns of how water crises can be managed and effectively communicated to people. The lessons learned from this peculiar context can then be compared with those of other areas that already experience water scarcity and, assuming that large shares of the population worldwide

at lower altitudes might have to deal with this issue in the future due to climate change, also transferred to other contexts.

In this pictorial, we report a **design journey** that alternated phases of divergence aimed at broadening horizons and fostering new insights and phases of convergence focused on exploring one or a few specific aspects within the expanded range of options [2]. Starting from the definition of the *challenge* outlined in this section, we engaged in a first divergent phase of *benchmarking* data physicalization artifacts related to water and mountains, followed by a convergent phase of *workshop materials preparation* where the insightful examples of data physicalization and the data collected during the interviews with mountain hut managers were transformed into practical materials to be used during a workshop to explore and generate a wide variety of *ideas*. Then, following the analysis of the ideas generated, we converged on two *concepts*, which were crafted into two video scenarios and foamboard prototypes. Finally, an *evaluation* of these concepts involving mountain hut managers was carried out.

Our design journey contributes to the ongoing discussion of Sustainable HCI in leveraging interactive experiences to convey both awareness of climate change-related issues (such as water scarcity in the mountains) and foster action [14]. The two concepts we distilled from our design process, a participatory installation and a serious game about decision-making, encourage physical interaction that fosters reflection on the relationship and mutual influence between individual visitors and the collective life of the mountain hut. By outlining the steps of our design process, we aim to inspire other HCI researchers and practitioners to distill contextual requirements, data, and educational purposes into tangible interactive artifacts.

BENCHMARKING DATA PHYSICALIZATIONS

Our design process started with a benchmark of significant examples of data physicalization representing water, with particular attention on water consumption, and encouraging awareness toward sustainability. We searched for examples on the dataphys.org website, which collects various artifacts, including research prototypes, historical tools, and art pieces exhibited in museums. In parallel, we also searched for literature conceptualizing data physicalization creation processes and communicative abilities on the ACM Digital Library.

Our final collection of data physicalizations included 12 examples, each representing water data in different ways, which served as initial inspiration and catalysts for the design process. To organize these examples, we analyzed and annotated them according to the following parameters: i) information/data being represented, ii) representation materials, shapes, and metaphors, iii) the relationship between the data and its representation (one-to-one, mathematically linked, or other), iv) the senses engaged, and v) the type of interaction offered and the related embodiment level. As for the interaction these physicalizations offered, we based our analysis on the design vocabulary for data physicalization proposed by [7], which categorizes various properties of data representations and was

Trends in Water
Adrien Segal, 2011

Certain Uncertainty
Schröder et al., 2023

The Data Soap
Clarice Lam, 2022

Digital Ethnography
Michelle Demmler, 2023

Arctic Sea Ice/Albedo
Adrien Segal, 2017

Edo
Sauve et al., 2023

Snow Water Equivalent
Adrien Segal, 2011

created to “inform design processes and highlight design strategies.” In particular, we draw on their conceptualization of explicit variables, i.e., characteristics derived from traditional visual variables used in data visualization but adapted to suit the multimodal nature of data physicalization, and implicit variables, i.e., the aspects that influence how users perceive and interact with the representation. Due to space limitations, we report just the most significant considerations emerging from our analysis.

Some physicalizations were designed as art exhibitions requiring no direct tactile interaction [11, 16, 17, 18, 19], while others were intended as participatory experiences leveraging extensively on embodiment [4, 15]. The exhibition pieces usually represented data from statistics and reports, such as the amount of water consumed yearly in the U.S.A. [18], the snowfall in

California over 30 years [19], the speed of Arctic ice melting [17], or the water stress in a few megacities of the planet [16]. Typically, these physicalizations used natural materials or materials that would mimic features of water or other natural elements, so that, despite not offering a tangible interaction, their materials would evoke intense tactile sensations through sight (synesthesia), e.g., water transparency in [15]. Segal’s work, in particular, leverages the agent power of nature by showing the texture of water excavation in the soil in [18] or the snow accumulation [19]. This line of research is taken forward by more recent HCI research, such as [25], which aims to move beyond water’s physical, aesthetic, and symbolic features and explicitly explore its agent nature as a more-than-human actor.

Other examples required a much higher level of embodied interaction. EDO [15] is a participatory installation where the data physicalization is generated by people's interaction. Users were called to express what food they had consumed during the day, and the physicalization would represent how many resources were used according to those dietary choices. Tokens were used to materialize personal behaviors, while physical bars represented the sum of individual contributions to resource consumption. Digital Ethnography [4] works similarly, although the topic is creating a 3D emotional map for recreational walks in the city of Kolding (DK). In both these interactive physicalizations, the materials chosen were more robust than evocative of water qualities since they were expected to be used by several people.

This review of data physicalization examples helped us understand how the design space of water data physicalization has been explored and populated so far. We used these insights to inspire the participants in our idea generation workshop, as well as inform the two final concepts we converged on.

IDEAS GENERATION WORKSHOP

We decided to conduct a brainstorming workshop to collect more ideas, and we structured it based on the methodology described by Huron et al. [8], which outlines the main steps for data physicalization workshops. Of the 5 phases they identified for the workshop, i.e., i) Data preparation, ii) Ideation, iii) Material selection, iv) Building the physicalization, and v) Reflecting on the physicalization, we put in place just number i), ii), and v), and left aside number iii) and iv) for a later refinement phase in which only the authors of this paper took part. This choice was due to a different goal for our workshop (collecting several ideas) compared to the educational purpose of Huron et al. (familiarizing participants with the production stages of data physicalization), and to time constraints. Our workshop took place during the participants' working hours; thus, we decided to make it last only 1 hour and a half, skipping the physical creation phase.

MATERIALS PREPARATION

Before the creative workshop, we embarked on a data curation phase [8, 23]. According to Huron et al. [8], preparing the data consists of "finding a dataset to work with, possibly collecting data or processing existing (digital) physical and material data into an adequate form". This phase is crucial to ensure the effectiveness of data physicalization workshops: it helps avoid participants getting stuck because they spend a lot of time looking for data that has not been processed yet.

To prepare the data for our workshop, we extracted precious knowledge about water availability, where and how water is taken, how it is stored, and how much is consumed (for cooking, flushing toilets, etc.) in each mountain hut from the 12 semi-structured interviews with mountain hut managers. Once the data were selected, analyzed, and refined, we developed three sets of cards to communicate this information effectively to the workshop participants. *Data cards*, *Activity cards*, and *Scenario cards* were produced as resources for the creative workshop. Their purpose was twofold: on the one hand, they served as constraints to make the workshop more efficient and focused, preventing the inclusion of irrelevant or broad data. On the other hand, they were designed to inspire participants and stimulate their creativity, encouraging ideas' playful and imaginative development by combining elements related to context, data, and goals.

Scenario cards

Scenario cards represent the different locations and contexts in which participants can imagine placing the physicalizations. While [8] provided urban scenario cards such as "the street", "business meeting", "home", "classroom", and "museum", we customized them to represent peculiar locations related to the mountain hut context. Initially, we also considered urban locations connected to the mountains, such as the local Alpine Club headquarters, museums, and cable car facilities. However, eventually, we decided to focus solely on mountainous areas, specifically along trails, near or inside mountain huts. The decision was driven by the need to focus the intervention on hut visitors and place the artifact within the context where the issue of water scarcity is most relevant, ensuring more significant engagement with the artifact and maximizing the impact of the physicalization. Therefore, the cards feature an illustration of hut-related environments and a title to identify them, namely, "Trail", "Outside the hut", "At the desk", "In the dining room", and "In the restroom".

Data cards

Data cards included the most relevant information about the mountain hut's water availability and consumption. Through them, we wanted to provide objective data and, at the same time, highlight the main problems of the huts. For example, showers have the highest impact on the huts' water reserve. In periods of drought, access to showers is denied, causing discontent in visitors who often have no experience of what it means to live and work in the mountains.

We developed 3 data cards. The first data card, "Water autonomy", presents a table with the following information for each of the interviewed mountain huts: name, water provisioning system (one or more among rainwater, glacier/snowmelt, spring), storage capacity, average daily consumption, and the resulting days of autonomy. The second data card, "Water consumption in the city and the hut", compares how much water each person consumes on average for activities such as cooking, washing dishes, showering, flushing toilets, personal hygiene, etc., at home and when staying at mountain huts. The only highlighted differences between the two locations were showering and flushing the toilet, which in mountain huts are typically set to use less water. The third data card, "Average daily water consumption per person", was a summary of the consumption by staff members (75 liters), visitors staying overnight (40 liters), visitors having only lunch (15 liters), and visitors only using the bathroom (6 liters).

By presenting these data cards at the beginning of the workshop, we meant to provide participants with an order of magnitude of the water consumption in mountain huts and the autonomy they have if they remain without water and ground the creative phase with real data from the case study we were going to design for.

Water autonomy

Mountain hut	Water supply system(s)	Storage Capacity (liters)	Average daily consumption (liters)	Days of autonomy
Boé		11400	5000	23
Stivo		80000	6000	13
Casinei		106000	5000	21
Vioz		39000	5500	7
Velo della Madonna		55000	1650	33
Capanna Piz Fassa		13000	3000	4
Alimonta		140000	9000	15
Casarota		40000	1800	20
Cornisello		11000	2500	4
Brentei		94000	12000	8
Water supply systems:		rainwater	Glacier/snowmelt	Spring

Water consumption per activity (city vs. hut)

Activity	Water used in the city	Water used in the hut
Drinking	2-2.5 liters	2-2.5 liters
Cooking	About 2 liters	About 2 liters
Showering	5 minutes equals 75-90 liters	2.5 minutes equals 40 liters
Toilet flushing	9 liters per flush	6 liters per flush
Personal hygiene	About 7.5 liters	About 7.5 liters
Washing machine	40-50 liters per cycle	40-50 liters per cycle
Dishwasher	10-12 liters per cycle	10-12 liters per cycle

Average daily water consumption per person

Person	Activity	Daily Water Consumption
		75 liters
		40 liters
		15 liters
		6 liters

Activity cards

Finally, we developed 7 activity cards that "contain a single descriptive word to evoke a high-level task" to foster reflection on the purpose of the physicalization envisioned and what kind of interaction it would enable. We used the six tasks proposed by [8], i.e., 'convince', 'discover', 'collect', 'enjoy', 'stimulate', and 'collaborate', plus, we added "contemplate" to take into account also the mountain setting and the reason for which visitors might reach mountain huts, i.e., nature contemplation.

Cooperate

Stimulate

Discover

Entertain

Convince

Collect

Contemplate

THE WORKSHOP

A workshop to generate a diverse range of data physicalization ideas was organized. It involved 6 participants, with the fourth author serving as facilitator. In addition to the first three authors (researchers in the fields of HCI and Data visualization), we involved people with different backgrounds who could bring a fresh perspective on data physicalization and water scarcity: an intern working in the field of HCI, a senior researcher expert of tangible interaction, and a software developer who is also an experienced ski mountaineering guide.

The workshop lasted 1 hour and a half, and the time was allocated as follows:

- 10 minutes were devoted to presenting the mountain huts' context and water-related challenges.
- 10 minutes to explain the concept of data physicalization, introduce the design vocabulary used in [5] to explain data physicalization features, and present six examples from the benchmarking.

- 10 minutes to explain the workshop goal (i.e., "How might we induce mountain hut visitors to reduce water consumption through a physical/tangible object?") and the data, activity, and scenario cards.
- 30 minutes for participants to produce at least three ideas individually. Participants were asked to outline their concepts on canvases we designed to collect ideas and scenarios in a structured way. The canvases included fields for participants to provide information about the data physicalization concept in written form, such as the name and a description or use scenario, as well as fields to specify the details about envisioned materials, the sensory qualities involved, the proposed location for the artifact, the desired duration of the interaction, the communicative intent, and the emotions aroused. Additionally, a space was allocated to represent the concept visually.
- In the last 30 minutes, participants shared their preferred ideas with the rest of the group.

Nome:
Descrizione/scenario d'uso:

"WATER TOKEN"

Si tratta di una fisicalizzazione dei dati partecipativa, pensata per riflettere i visitatori sui consumi in un rifugio come ad esempio: consumare un pasto, lavarsi i denti, fare una doccia.

Il concept prevede che ogni escursionista abbia una limitata quantità di **TOKEN** che possono essere usati negli spazi del rifugio quando si compiono attività che prevedono l'utilizzo di acqua.

L'installazione prevede che il visitatore metta i suoi token in colonne in **PLEXIGLAS** in modo che sono visibili su che i token giù meno degli altri visitatori.

ESEMPLO: una colonna fosse in **BANNO** raccoglie i token relativi al consumo di acqua: Toilette + LAVABO.

Rappresentazione grafica:

Durata dell'interazione: la permanenza in rifugio
Dove lo trovo/uso: luoghi dove si utilizza L'ACQUA: BANO, SALA da PRANZO
Materiali: Plexiglas, Vetro o Legno per i TOKENS
Qualità sensoriali: interazione tattile con i token
Intento comunicativo: consapevolezza dei consumi Collettivi
Emozione suscitata: CURIOSITÀ, SPIRITO di COLLABORAZIONE.

IDEAS GENERATED

Sixteen data physicalization ideas emerged from the workshop. We digitalized the written descriptions to allow a shared analysis between the authors, which was inspired by the annotated portfolio technique [5]. Below, we report an account of all the ideas produced, focusing on the most representative details.

Location. Most ideas were designed to be situated inside the mountain hut, while the few placed outside were meant to be found along the path leading to it. Reasonably, data physicalizations in the hut are smaller due to the limited space available, while those outside are more voluminous. For example, "Columns of Future", which are intended to be found along the path, consisted of big columns of plexiglass placed every 2 km and filled with different quantities of water representing how much it snowed in the 1980s, 2000s, 2020s, and the forecast for the 2040s.

Materials. As for the materials envisaged, 11 out of 16 physicalizations involved glass, plexiglass, or transparent plastic, chosen primarily for their transparency. In those ideas, water was the key element of the physicalization. For example, 'Light of water' consisted of making the water tanks transparent and placing them in a visible spot outside the hut. Becoming a central piece of the hut rather than a hidden infrastructure, the water tank could be observed both in its consumption and the beauty of water, especially when sunrays hit it, and the water's transparency and reflection could be appreciated.

Evocative vs. Interactive. Some ideas required direct interaction, while others were more evocative. Among the evocative ones is a "Snow globe" filled with water and a small hut model without snow. When turned upside down, rather than little white pieces falling like snow, the sound of a melting glacier would be played. This idea aims to generate curiosity and awareness about the reduction or lack of snow in the mountains. Another contemplative idea was "Waterballs", a simple installation of balls of different sizes filled with water hanging by a thread from the bathroom ceiling with

messages like "shower = 40 liters". This installation was intended to be a reminder and raise awareness. Amidst evocative and interactive is the "Graduated carafe". A carafe filled with drinkable water is provided at each table during meals. The carafe presents ticks on its surface with captions like "flushing the toilet = -6 liters", reminding the user of the actual impact of everyday activities on the mountain hut resources. In this case, the representation of data is neither linear nor accurate since there is no direct correlation between the amount of water visitors drop in their glasses and the activity of filling the glass, but the intention is to stimulate discussions during collective meals with others and, thus, increase awareness.

Individual vs. collective interaction. The ideas requiring people's interaction could be divided into those intended for individual use and those conceived as participatory, encouraging the active involvement of more visitors. An idea requiring individual interaction is "Clepsydra", which consists of a physical hourglass placed on the shower pipe, representing in real-time the speed with which the allocated water for each shower gets consumed. Conversely, examples of collective interactions are 'Water token' and 'Balancing'. In 'Water tokens', when a visitor reaches the hut to spend the

night, at the check-in, they are told that for their stay (evening-night-morning), they can consume a maximum of 40 liters of water, and are given water tokens to spend. Transparent tubes will be installed in front of the bathrooms and the dining room, with holes at the top to allow the insertion of tokens each time a visitor uses water for activities in those settings. For those who manage to save their tokens, it is possible to share them with other hikers, put them in the column for animals, or exchange them for different activities with an equivalent value of liters. In 'Balancing', a two-arm scale is installed in the main room of the hut: the first arm holds a miniature reconstruction of the refuge, whose weight represents its water reserve. In the second plate, hikers who use the sanitary facilities insert a marble whose weight corresponds to the average amount of water used with the action performed. This physicalization allows visitors to observe how their water use affects the scale's balance in real time. As long as the weight of the marbles is lighter than the weight of the miniature of the refuge, a green LED remains on, indicating that the water consumption is sustainable. When the weight of the marbles exceeds the weight of the hut, the LED gradually changes color from green to red, signaling excessive and unsustainable water consumption.

CLEPSYDRA

SNOW GLOBE

BALANCING

GRADUATED CARAFE

WATER TOKEN

LIGHT OF WATER

COLUMNS OF FUTURE

WATER BALLS

DEVELOPING TWO CONCEPTS

This section describes the two data physicalization concepts we distilled from the ideas generated during the workshop. Analyzing the ideas generated provided us with a repository of inspiring elements that could be combined to develop new ideas. Prioritizing our focus on water consumption at the hut and creating an artefact that could merge with the hut environment and activities, we took inspiration mostly from "Water token" and "Balancing", while we discarded features like the sound of the glacier melting or the size of the Columns of the future.

FRAMING WATER

"Framing Water" is a serious game aimed at stimulating individual reflection and raising awareness among visitors about the impact of their water consumption behavior during their stay at the mountain hut. By physically constraining the amount of water each visitor can use (estimated at 40 liters), players must choose how much water to consume by eating, drinking, flushing the toilet, or showering. This prompts decision-making about water consumption, challenging users to allocate their usage thoughtfully while staying within the limits. The goal is to promote reflection on the fact that natural resources are limited and that conscious choices should be made for their equitable distribution.

Physicalized Data

"Framing Water" materializes the optimal amount of

water for a single visitor during an overnight stay in a wooden frame, which can contain up to 40 liters and serve as a support and a boundary for tiles.

The amount of water required for individual activities is represented by semi-transparent squared tiles: a single tile represents 1 liter of water and corresponds to brushing teeth; 4 connected tiles represent the 4 liters of water required by meal cooking and related dishwashing; 6 tiles (6 liters) correspond to flushing the toilet or personal hygiene. Finally, a piece of 40 tiles (40 liters) corresponds to a 2.5-minute-long shower. Since the frame maximum occupation is 40 tiles, having a shower hits the limit by itself, thus suggesting it is a better-to-avoid activity since it exceeds the average water consumption and severely impacts the hut's water reserve.

Properties and materials

During the design phase, we evaluated different frame and piece shapes. Foamboard mock-ups were produced to see which shape could better support the interaction and trigger reflections. We explored various approaches to balance the challenge of filling the frame and ensuring that the activity remains enjoyable and achievable. Initially, inspired by Tangram [22], irregular triangle shapes were examined, but finally, same-size square pieces were preferred for their modularity and ease of combination. The materials chosen for this type of physicalization are wood for the frame, and a radiant acrylic plexiglass with a wavy water-effect surface and a polished back for the tiles.

FRAMES FROM FRAMING WATER'S VIDEO SCENARIO

Interaction and setting

This playful data physicalization is targeted at visitors who stay overnight and have some time to engage with it. It is a game that visitors can play, for example, after dinner. The visitors choose the chains of tiles representing the activities (eating, using the toilet, drinking, or taking a shower) they plan to do during their stay and try to fit these pieces inside the frame. In doing so, they engage in a tangible sustainability exercise, which invites them to reflect on the balance between their choices and the limited resources available. Filling the frame is not easy since it introduces a constraint that forces users to consider the number and combination of tiles chosen. Making choices on the consumption of limited water resources takes time but stimulates reflection. For instance, visitors will tangibly experience that a shower in a mountain hut consumes the equivalent amount of water allocated to an individual visitor for an entire day.

This playful data physicalization is inspired by the "Tangram" [22], but unlike it, the goal is not necessarily to fill the entire frame. Indeed, if some spaces are left empty, this could be further rewarded because it would mean that the person could consume less than the 40 liters of water assigned to them. The game is designed primarily for individual use. However, given the communal context of mountain huts that naturally fosters informal interactions among visitors or with the hut manager, the artifact is expected to work as a conversation starter, prompting discussions about water scarcity and, thus, deepening the visitors' understanding of the challenges related to water conservation in such a resource-limited context.

UNBALANCED

"Unbalanced" is a participatory installation designed to increase the mountain hut visitors' awareness of the weight of their actions on the hut's water resources. It consists of a balance scale with a horizontal bar and two hanging plates to weigh objects. On one plate, there is a representation of the hut water reserve; on the other, visitors can add a physical representation of their water consumption during their stay and see how it affects the overall water reserve. This concept targets all visitors, including those stopping by the hut for a few hours to have lunch and use the bathroom. Moreover, unlike "Framing Water", consumption is considered collectively, and visitors' impact is provided through an aggregated view.

Physicalized Data

In "Unbalanced", the represented data are the estimated water consumption of three types of mountain hut guests: 80 liters for those staying overnight and taking a shower, 40 liters for visitors staying overnight but not having a shower, and 10 liters for those who only eat a meal and use the toilet. These water consumption data are contrasted with water availability data, i.e., the estimated water available daily in the three conditions: the ideal period when the hut has plenty of water, the intermediate period in which there is no overflowing water, but the hut storage tanks are full and so it has still some days of autonomy, and the critical period when the availability of water is minimal, it has not rained for many weeks, and the manager might need to take harsh measures, such as closing toilets, calling the helicopter for bringing water, or even closing the hut.

Properties and materials

The squared shape of cubes was preferred over the marbles of the initial concept as it avoids them rolling on the floor in case they are accidentally dropped. As for the materials, it was decided to use wood, both for the scale and the cubes representing water, having those for consumption painted in blue, as it better integrates with the mountain hut environment.

Interaction and setting

The interaction with the scale foresees two types of users: the hut staff and the visitors. Each morning, the hut staff is expected to place a cube whose weight represents the estimated daily water availability according to the situation in which the hut is at that moment and to empty the other plate from the visitors' cubes. This activity would take place every morning after the overnight guests' departure and before the new guests' arrival. When the new guests arrive, they can pick the cube that reflects their water consumption from one of the three transparent dispensers near the scale and put it on the second plate. Once the cubes are placed, visitors can watch the plates settle. If the scale balance is still in favor of the hut, it means that water availability is more than demand, and the plate is lit with a green LED. When visitors' water consumption exceeds the hut's water reserve, the LED becomes red, signaling the unsustainability of the situation. To attract attention and encourage participation, the participatory data physicalization installation is intended to be placed in a central location in the mountain hut, such as by the cash register desk, and be accompanied by a sign explaining what it is and how it works.

FRAMES FROM UNBALANCED'S VIDEO SCENARIO

CONCEPTS EVALUATION

To validate the two concepts, we conducted a first evaluation with the same mountain hut managers we interviewed in the beginning. Since it was high season in the mountains by the time we were ready to show them our concepts, we deemed it more practical to reach them remotely and collect data through WhatsApp voice notes [13]. To share and explain our two concepts more easily, we prepared two short videos (2 and 3 minutes long) with voiceovers (available as additional materials to this pictorial). Both videos show the brief story of a mountain hut visitor who finds and uses the concepts to explain the intended interaction, motivation, and possible outcomes. Nine mountain hut managers agreed to participate in the evaluation. We sent them two videos and asked them to respond with text messages or voice notes, answering 6 questions for each video. The questions included:

- *What do you think of this idea?* To gather general feedback on the concept presented in the video.
- *Would it help make visitors more aware of water scarcity?* To evaluate the concept's effectiveness in raising awareness and encouraging behavior change.
- *Would you place it in your hut?* To determine whether managers found the physicalization suitable for their huts.
- *Do you think your hut guests would use it?* To assess the likelihood of the physicalization engaging guests and sparking their interest.
- *Is there anything that doesn't convince you? What would you change?* To identify weaknesses in the concept and collect suggestions for improvement.
- *Which of the two ideas is your preferred one?* To prompt them to express which idea might hold more potential.

The "Unbalanced" concept was well appreciated, the main strength being that it allows many people to interact, which could be a powerful means of engagement and discussion. The managers felt the message conveyed through the data physicalization was clear and effectively communicated: it suggests that the problem affects all and that, to solve it, we need to help each other. The main downside is that it requires a dedicated space, and spaces and furniture are minimal in mountain huts. Moreover, respondents agreed that explanatory materials must accompany the artifact, as mountain hut managers are often very busy and may not have the time to explain them to visitors personally. Without this support, there is a risk that the data physicalization will remain underutilized. Another concern was that, as a collaborative installation, if only a few visitors engage with it and place their tokens, the data represented might not accurately reflect the actual situation. This could potentially convey a distorted message, undermining the communicative efficacy of the data physicalization.

Regarding "Framing Water", the main advantage highlighted by the managers is that it is contained in a box and does not take up too much space. It can be closed, placed away, and given to visitors when desired. Many huts already have board games, playing cards, and books that visitors can use for free during their stay, so if placed among other board games, it might be taken out of curiosity and used without the need for the manager to push its use. Unlike "Unbalanced", it allows for a deeper understanding of how much water individual activities consume, and for this reason, it was perceived as more appropriate and effective. The main criticism was that it was not easy to understand how it works from the video alone. In this case, we believe a prototype would be more effective in conveying the idea since details such as how the tiles are built, how to place them, and their translucence were not easy to represent in a video scenario.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

This pictorial showcases a design process that explored how data physicalizations can effectively convey the idea of limits in relation to water resources in mountain huts to encourage visitors to reduce their water consumption. Our goal was to make water consumption tangible to ground visitors' understanding of the water scarcity problem through first-hand experiences and to focus on the concept of "limit". To this end, mountain huts offer an interesting setting, as their social nature (being a collective place) and separated nature (being isolated) make them an ideal laboratory to experiment with solutions that can inspire other communities experiencing the same problem.

Through our design exploration, we developed two data physicalization concepts (a participatory installation and a serious game about decision-making), encouraging physical interaction that fosters reflection on the relationship and mutual influence between individual visitors and the collective life of the mountain hut. These concepts are the results of several reflections and highlight key opportunities and challenges in the development of data physicalizations. By outlining the steps of our design process, we aim to inspire other HCI researchers and practitioners to distill contextual requirements, data, and educational purposes into tangible interactive artifacts.

Designing for remote, off-grid contexts

Contextual constraints have been considered since the beginning of our exploration and profoundly affected all the choices we made throughout our design journey. Mountain huts are remote buildings that provide shelter and essential services in harsh environments. Typically, they do not have direct access to public utilities, thus relying on self-sufficient, off-grid infrastructures that offer limited access to water, electricity, and the Internet. Furthermore, space within the hut is limited and characterized by shared use, and in high season, the staff have scarce time and resources to dedicate to extra activities besides those necessary to run the hut. These factors significantly influenced several design

choices, such as the material selected for the concepts, which needed to be at the same time natural and robust to bear the use of many people, and the choice to reduce digital interactivity to a minimum (see the LED in "Unbalanced") to avoid relying on electricity and internet connection to make the data physicalization work. Other constraints that we considered were related to the acceptability of the artifacts. In this respect, the two concepts that were developed require minimal maintenance and can be used autonomously by visitors.

Data between accuracy and evocativeness

A second challenge we faced was choosing whether to pursue the mathematical accuracy of data representation or its evocative power. Data accuracy refers to how accurately a physical representation reflects the underlying data, including precise measurements and correct relationships. Evocativeness (also referred to as 'affective engagement' [24] or 'qualitative aspects of data' [24]), on the other hand, involves the ability of a physical artifact to engage users emotionally or sensorially, making the data more relatable through metaphors, similarity, assonance, etc. [11, 24]. In Framing Water, we strove to reach the mathematical accuracy of data related to individual consumption to make each visitor reflect on their actual consumption. In that concept, we fostered engagement through the playfulness of the interaction. Conversely, in 'Unbalanced', we sought a more evocative representation of collective data since interacting with it is optional for guests and, consequently, the representation of data could hold some uncertainty. Still, by relating two quantities - the water available and the water consumed - the installation can foster reflection in those who choose to engage with it on the cumulative effects of individual behaviors and show that even a short stay at the hut can impact its water reserve.

"It's a good idea, in my opinion. It conveys the concept of consumption well, also because it immediately promotes the idea of community and unity, and the fact that we need to help each other to thrive, and it becomes immediately clear."

A mountain hut manager
commenting on 'Framing Water'

Provoking thoughts, triggering conversations

Throughout the design process, several considerations emerged on how to foster engagement with the issue of water scarcity. In this regard, design choices were made first to engage visitors at multiple levels. The first engagement invitation was through playful interaction, but then, in our intention, it should be followed by reflection and sparking potential conversation. While in "Framing Water", the engagement is initially individual, and the expectation is that the intimate and communal atmosphere of mountain huts helps attract attention also from other visitors and spark discussions and participation, Unbalanced is designed intentionally as a participatory installation which aims at raising awareness by representing the collective behavior.

Facing the limit

The two concepts unpack the limit concept by fostering reflection on the relationship and mutual influence between individual visitors and the collective life of the mountain hut. We physicalized the idea of limits differently by relating individual and collective water consumption to the water available in the mountain hut in two concepts. In "Framing Water", the limit is static, represented as a wooden frame containing 40 tiles corresponding to the 40 liters, the amount of water a visitor is expected to consume during an overnight stay in the hut. In "Unbalanced", the limit is dynamic: the hut manager can use the installation to communicate the current state of the hut's water reserve. Here, the limit is more flexible and negotiable: the data on water availability are less accurate but can more effectively represent the varying states of resources in the hut that have been synthesized in three different states (from no to enough water available). This reflects the fact that, depending on weather conditions (rain, snow, etc.) and the number of visitors, water reservoirs can fluctuate.

In conclusion, our design work contributes to the ongoing discussion of Sustainable HCI about leveraging interactive experiences to convey both awareness of climate change-related issues, such as water scarcity in the mountains, and foster action motivated by the common good rather than personal gain.

LIMITATION OF FUTURE WORK

We are aware that the evaluation of the two concepts cannot be considered exhaustive since we involved only mountain hut managers and not visitors. To get direct feedback from the intended users of these data physicalizations, we plan to prototype the two concepts and leave them in at least a mountain hut during the spring-summer of 2025.

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